
Socio-cultural Problems faced by eunuchs living in district Jamshoro: A Sociological Analysis

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Abstract

The present study focuses on socio-cultural problems of eunuchs living in district Jamshoro. There are many problems faced by eunuchs in their daily life such as disown by family, lack of education, unemployment, exploitation, physical, verbal, mental and sexual abuse, torture, rape and security of life. This study covers the social and cultural problems and also suggestions to resolve these problems. The present research is pure quantitative and primary method was used. Data was collected through closed ended questionnaire and it is descriptive research. Census method was used and the number of respondents according to census report 2017 was forty four. This research includes both descriptive and inferential statistics i.e. data was analyzed through percentage tables and Hypotheses were tested by using Chi Square test of independence in SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences).

Keywords: Eunuch, Socio- Cultural problems, disown by family, sexual abuse.

1. Introduction

This research is about social and cultural problems faced by eunuchs living in Jamshoro. The word eunuch is combination of two greek words, eune means bed and ekhein means to keep, so they were the bed keepers (Oxford Dictionary, 2019) . In Pakistan, people call them hijra, khusra, khawajasira and in Sindh language, people call them khadra faqeer.

Eunuchs living in Pakistan are in miserable conditions as it took more than seventy years to accept them as citizen of Pakistan. In 2012, Government issued them national identity cards and for the first time, they voted in elections (Raza, 2012).

1.2 Historical Background

Eunuchs had great importance in Mughal era as they were guards of personal rooms of rulers. They were part of judiciary, military, and other institutions like politics and religion (Jami, 2005). Eunuchs not only lost their strong positions in different institutions but they completely lost their basic rights under British rule in 1870 (Abbas, Ali, & Nawaz, 2014).

1.3 Social and Cultural Problems

Since birth, eunuchs faces socio cultural problems such as disown by their own family, lack of education, low prestige, cultural barriers, lack of safety and no governmental support. Their own family disowns them just because of their gender as third gender is considered disgrace for family's honour and they begin to live under shadows of poverty. They are deprived of their rights such as right to education, right to safety etc.

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1.3.1 Education

Mostly eunuchs living in Pakistan are illiterate and there are many reasons behind it. Their own family disowns them so they did not get even a single chance to go to school and study. Fortunately, if they get admission in school, due to the rigid behaviour of teachers and fellow students, they are bound to leave the school as they experience personal insecurity in school in initial stages of their life. Fellow students mock them, taunt them and sometimes even torture them mentally and physically (Berk, 1999).

1.3.2 Cultural Norms

Cultural norms means pattern of behaviour of society with eunuchs. Eunuchs living in Pakistan are involved in prostitution, begging and dancing because of lacking socially approved economic opportunities as our society restricted them to such works (Lal, 1999).

1.3.3 Disown by Family

Eunuchs are disowned by the family just because of their gender as there is no social acceptance of third gender in Pakistani society. People feel disgraceful to have eunuch as family member. Disowning by family is the root cause of other problems that eunuchs face as their own family is not ready to accept them. (Khalid, 2015).

1.3.4 Lack of Safety

Eunuchs are the most vulnerable group of society and security of life is one of the most important problems of eunuchs. Mostly at night, they go out in markets to beg and dance in functions and they face verbal, physical and sexual abuse and many eunuchs even have lost their lives. Police do not give them protection (Khalid, 2015).

1.3.5 Low Prestige

Usually people do not respect eunuchs due to their gender and the work they do to survive i.e. prostitution, begging and dancing. Education and good occupation can increase their social respect in society (Amna Nasir, 2013)

1.3.6 Exploitation

Due to a particular mindset of society towards eunuchs, eunuchs are exploited by the society at all levels such as family, school, or neighborhood. They are exploited due to their dressing, way of talking and the work they do to earn.

2. Objectives

1. To investigate the socio-cultural problems of eunuchs living in Jamshoro.
2. To suggest policies for the safety of eunuchs in Jamshoro.

3. Literature Review

The most ignored group of society is group of eunuchs. Their own family members disown them and they get their early socialization with in eunuch community where they live in shadows of poverty and sex work. People verbally, sexually, physically and mentally abuse them. They get involve in sex work, begging and they dance to earn because our society has

nothing to offer them and people usually do not accept them as part of society. As a citizen of Pakistan, it is their right to get education, employment and live with dignity and honor but they are forced into work like sex work (Khalid, 2015).

Lives of eunuchs are not safe as many of the eunuchs face torture by their clients and sometimes by family members and neighbors. Many eunuchs are gang raped by clients and in many cases clients also record videos while committing this heinous crime. Usually eunuchs do not make complain against culprits as majority of eunuchs do not trust police as they are also harassed by police officer (Aurat Foundation, 2016).

A eunuch named shama who was just eighteen years old was gang raped by nine men and then she was brutally murdered. In sahiwal, eunuch named munnai was killed after she did not dance for the whole night. There are countless cases reported where eunuchs are brutally murdered by their family members, clients and influential people and no even one eunuch got justice (Rimmel Mohyidin, 2018).

National Assembly passed a bill to give rights to eunuchs which includes right to inheritance, property, vote etc (Redding, 2019) .

4. Material and Methods

Primary method of research is used and data was collected through close ended questionnaires. This research is descriptive research as much is known about the problem under investigation and it is pure quantitative research. Universe includes all the eunuchs living in district Jamshoro. Jamshoro includes four tehsils i.e. Majhand, Thano bula khan, Kotri and Sehwan. Researcher used the census method and according to census 2017 in Pakistan, there were forty four eunuchs living in Jamshoro (Units & Pakhtunkhwa, 2017). Majority of the respondents was illiterate; researcher translated the questionnaire in their native language and explained each question to respondents. Chi Square was used to test the hypotheses in SPSS version 20.

5. Results and Interpretations

Results include both descriptive and inferential statistics as simple percentage method was used and hypotheses were also tested applying Chi Square test of independence.

Table:: Table showing percentage distribution of respondent's answers to questions related with Socio-cultural factors.

Education of Respondents	Primary (31.8%)	Illiterate (68.2%)
Socially Respected	Yes (36.4%)	No (63.6%)
Socially Approved Economic Opportunities	Yes (27%)	No (72.7%)
Occupation	Begging (43.2%)	Dancing (56.8%)
Safety at Work	Yes (6.8%)	No (93.2%)
Separate Education System for Eunuchs	Yes (9.1%)	No (90.9%)
Feeling of being Eunuch	Ashamed (4.5%)	Sad (95.5%)
Reason of leaving Family	Family Pressure (90.9%)	Comfortable with eunuchs (9.1%)

Family's invitation at functions	Yes (18.2%)	No (81.8%)
Family's invitation at funerals	Yes (18.2%)	No (81.8%)
Appearance when visiting Family	Male (93.2%)	Female (6.8%)
Behaviour of Family on visit	Good (6.8%)	Bad (93.2%)
Behaviour of Neighbors	Good (9.1%)	Bad (90.9%)
Verbally abused	Yes (100%)	No (0%)
Sexually Harassed	Yes (100%)	No (0%)
Faced Torture	Yes (97.7%)	No (2.3%)
Voted in Elections	Yes (2.3%)	No (97.7%)
Allowed to enter mosque/ temple	Yes (9.1%)	No (90.9%)

Interpretation of Results

Above tables shows that 68.2% of the respondents were illiterate and only 31.8% of the respondents got education up to primary. The majority i.e. 63.6% said no, they are not socially respected while 36.4% said yes. The majority i.e. 72.7% of the respondents said no, they do not have socially approved economic opportunities while 27% said yes. The majority i.e. 56.8% said that dancing at functions is their occupation while 43.2% said begging. The majority of the respondents i.e. 93.2% said no, we do not feel safe while going out for work and only 6.8% said yes. The majority i.e. 90.9% of the respondents said that they feel sad being eunuch while 4.5% said they are ashamed of being eunuch. The majority of the respondents i.e. 90.9% said they left family due to family pressure while only 9.1% said they feel comfortable with other eunuchs. The majority i.e. 81.8% said that they are not invited by the family to attend family functions and funerals while only 18.2% said yes, they are invited. Majority of the respondents i.e. 93.2% said they prefer male appearance when they visit family while 6.8% said female appearance. The majority i.e. 93.2% said that the behaviour of family with eunuchs is bad while 6.8% said that the behaviour is good. The majority i.e. 90.9% said that the behaviour of neighbors with eunuchs is bad while 9.1% said behaviour of neighbors is good. All the respondents i.e. 100% of the respondents said they are verbally abused and sexually harassed. The majority i.e. 97.7% said they faced torture while 2.3% said no, they never faced it. The majority i.e. 97.7% said no, they never voted in elections while 2.3% said yes, they have voted. The majority i.e. 90.9% said that they are not allowed to enter mosques/temples while only 9.1% said yes, they are allowed to enter.

4.1 Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1:

Ho: "There is no relationship between Cultural norms and Exploitation of eunuchs".

H1: "There is a relationship between Cultural norms and Exploitation of eunuchs"

Test: Chi-Square test of independence

Significant Level: 0.05

Df: 1

Cross Tabulation between Socially approved economic opportunities and Current work

		Current work		Total	
		Begging	Dancing		
Does society provides Socially approved economic opportunities?	Yes	Result	(9f)	(3f)	(12f)
		Estimated Result	(5.2f)	(6.8f)	(12.0f)
	No	Result	(10f)	(22f)	(32f)
		Estimated Result	(13.8f)	(18.2f)	(32.0f)
Total		Result	(19f)	(25f)	(44f)
		Estimated Result	(19.0f)	(25.0f)	(44.0f)

(Chi Square Test)

	(Value)	(DF)	(Asymp. Sig) (2-sided)	(Exact Sig) (2-sided)	(Exact Sig) (1-sided)
(Pearson's Chi Square)	6.808 ^a	1	.009		
(Continuity Correction)	5.142	1	.023		
(Likelihood-Ratio)	6.931	1	.008		
(Fisher Exact-Test)				.016	.
(Linear by Linear Association)	6.654	1	.010		
(Valid Cases)	44				
a. (0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.18)					
b. (Computed only for a 2x2 table)					

The Null hypothesis is rejected because the probability value 0.009 is less than significant value 0.05. Further the Computed value 6.808 is greater than tabulated value 3.84.

Hypothesis 2:

Ho: "There is no relationship between /Education of eunuchs and Prestige".

H1: "There is a relationship between "Education of eunuchs and Prestige"

Test: Chi-Square test of independence

Significant Level: 0.05

Df: 1

Cross Tabulation between Education and Socially Respected

			Socially Respected		Total
			Yes	No	
Education	Primary	Result	11f	3f	14f
		Estimated Result	5.1f	8.9f	14.0f
	Illiterate	Result	5f	25f	30f
		Estimated Result	10.9f	19.1f	30.0f
Total		Result	16f	28f	44f
		Estimated Result	16.0f	28.0f	44.0f

(Chi Square)

	(Value)	(DF)	(Asymp. Sig) (2-sided)	(Exact Sig) (2- sided)	(Exact Sig) (1- sided)
(Pearson's Chi Square)	15.808 ^a	1	.000		
(Continuity Correction)	13.246	1	.000		
(Likelihood-Ratio)	16.100	1	.000		
(Fisher Exact-Test)				.000	.000
(Linear by Linear Association)	15.449	1	.000		
(Valid Cases)	44				
a. (0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.09)					
b. (Computed only for a 2x2 table)					

The Null hypothesis is rejected because the probability value 0.000 is less than significant value 0.05. Further the computed value 15.808 is greater than tabulated value 3.84.

4.1.3 Hypothesis 3:

Ho: "There is no relationship between Lack of government policies and worst safety of eunuchs".

H1: "There is a relationship between "lack of government policies and worst safety of eunuchs"

Test: Chi-Square test of independence

Significant Level: 0.05

Df: 1

Is the government working for your rights? * Do you feel safe during current government's tenure? Cross tabulation					
			Do you feel safe during current government's tenure?		Total
			Yes	No	
Is the government working for your rights?	Yes	Result	11f	4f	15f
		Estimated Result	5.1f	9.9f	15.0f
	No	Result	4f	25f	29f
		Estimated Result	9.9f	19.1f	29.0f
Total		Result	15f	29f	44f
		Estimated Result	15.0f	29.0f	44.0f

(Chi Square Test)					
	(Value)	(DF)	(Asymp. Sig) (2-sided)	(Exact Sig) (2-sided)	(Exact Sig) (1-sided)
(Pearson's Chi Square)	15.598 ^a	1	.000		
(Continuity Correction)	13.061	1	.000		
(Likelihood-Ratio)	15.798	1	.000		
(Fisher Exact-Test)				.000	.000
(Linear by Linear Association)	15.244	1	.000		
(Valid Cases)	44				
a. (0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.11)					
b. (Computed only for a 2x2 table)					

The Null hypothesis is rejected because the probability value 0.000 is less than significant value 0.05. The Computed value 15.598 is great than 3.84.

6. Conclusion

From the findings, it is pretty much clear that eunuchs are living in miserable conditions. They are facing socio cultural problems like lack of education, unemployment, lack of safety,

disown by family, no government or non government support, no cultural support, sexual, mental, physical and verbal abuse, torture and exploitation. Our society has nothing to offer to eunuchs except, begging, sex work or dancing. Majority of the respondents were illiterate and they were not satisfied with their lives as they are deprived of their basic human rights.

7. Suggestions:

1. Government should ensure rights of eunuchs such as education, employment, primary health care, security of life and all other rights exercised by the man and women of this country.
2. Civil society and NGOs should work for the betterment of eunuchs by arranging awareness programs about problems faced by eunuchs.
3. Families should be strictly warned of not to disown their baby due to gender.
4. There should be a proper record of eunuchs i.e. education, fertility, mortality, health etc
5. Courses should be included like gender studies or knowledge about third gender so that people can understand the problems of eunuchs and help them to resolve those problems.

References

1. Abbas, T., Ali, M., & Nawaz, R. (2014). *Social Adjustment of Transgender : A Study of District Chiniot , Punjab (Pakistan)*. 3(1), 61-72. <https://doi.org/10.5901/ajis.2014.v3n1p61>
2. Amna Nasir. (2013). The tale of transgender people: When hate starts ruining lives. Retrieved from BLOGS The Express Tribune website: <https://blogs.tribune.com.pk/story/15948/the-tale-of-transgender-people-when-hate-starts-ruining-lives/>
3. Aurat Foundation. (2016). *Silent no more: Transgender community in Pakistan - A research study*. Retrieved from https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PBAAF371.pdf
4. Berk, L. (1999). *Infants, Children, and Adolescents*. Retrieved from <https://www.amazon.com/Infants-Children-Adolescents-Berk-Meyers/dp/0133936732>
5. Jami, H. (2005). Condition and Status of Hijras (Transgender, Transvestites etc.) in Pakistan. *1st International Conference of Asian Queer Studies*. Retrieved from <http://www.asylumlaw.org/docs/sexualminorities/PakistanHijras123105.pdf>
6. Khalid, I. (2015). Eunuchs in Pakistan- The unwanted gender. Retrieved from PAK TEA HOUSE website: <http://pakteahouse.net/2015/02/04/eunuchs-in-pakistan-the-unwanted-gender/>
7. Lal, V. (1999). Not This, Not That: The Hijras of India and the Cultural Politics of Sexuality. *Social Text*, pp. 119-140. <https://doi.org/10.2307/488683>
8. Raza, T. (2012). EUNUCHS- A NEGLECTED CHAPTER OF PAKISTANI SOCIETY. Retrieved from Talal exploring life with pen website: <https://talalraza.wordpress.com/2012/07/16/eunuchs-a-neglected-chapter-of-pakistani-society/>
9. Redding, J. A. (2019). The Pakistan Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act of 2018 and Its Impact on the Law of Gender in Pakistan. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, (2010), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3339759>
10. Rimmel Mohyidin. (2018). With transgender rights, Pakistan has an opportunity to be a pathbreaker. Retrieved from Dawn News website: <https://www.dawn.com/news/1450616>
11. Units, A., & Pakhtunkhwa, K. (2017). *District wise population by sex and rural/urban Government of Pakistan*.